

The use cases

Deterministic services for critical communications

at the Nokia Budapest Open Lab

This use case lays out a challenging multi-modal mobility scenario coupled with deterministic needs that serves as a good test for the multi-domain autonomous deterministic network architecture proposed by PREDICT-6G.

Multi-domain deterministic communication

at the Madrid Open Lab (STONIC)

PREDICT-6G will demonstrate through this use case the extension of deterministic communications to large-scale scenarios in a multi-provider scenario by exploring a combination of control and data-plane mechanisms to ensure in-time and on-time services.

Smart Manufacturing

at the Ericsson Madrid Open Lab (STONIC)

This use case provides wireless access with deterministic characteristics to robots controlled in the cloud, using the innovations on disaggregated architectures expected in 6G, advancing towards the model of the future smart manufacturing plant.

About PREDICT-6G

Start date: 01 January 2023

Duration: 30 months

Overall budget: € 6,082,687.50

Topic: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-01 - System Architecture

Key objectives: set towards the development of an E2E 6G solution including architecture and protocols that can guarantee seamless provisioning of services for vertical use cases requiring extremely tight timing and reliability constraints

The Team

PREDICT-6G consortium brings together a team of experts from **17** organisations across **8** countries, including **2** affiliated entities.

17

ORGANISATIONS

8

COUNTRIES

2

AFFILIATED ENTITIES

PREDICT-6G

Connectivity.
Reliability.
Quality.
Security.

**Towards a deterministic
6G network:
reliable, time sensitive
and predictable**

Funded by
the European Union

Why PREDICT-6G?

We foresee to change the networking paradigm creating a deterministic network (time sensitive, reliable and predictable), fostering new business cases and applications, and powering up the waited for digitalisation of the industry.

The Challenges

01

Varying definition and description of determinism per domain

02

Different capabilities on the data-plane to achieve determinism with a lack of proper standardized APIs

03

Different intrinsic network capabilities due to various link layer technologies

04

Incompatible control- and management plane interfaces related to the provisioning of determinism

Our Approach

The **PREDICT-6G** project aims to create a secure, modular, interoperable, and extensible deterministic network and management framework that automates the definition, provisioning, monitoring, fulfillment, and life-cycle management of E2E deterministic services over multiple network domains, **hiding the complexity of continuously balancing and re-configuring the constituent domain specific enablers to maintain a consistent E2E determinism.**

PREDICT-6G builds on top of three pillars

To extend the reliability and time sensitiveness features of IEEE 802.11 and 3GPP networks, including APIs for the monitoring and control of such capabilities, enabling predictability.

To develop a Multi- Technology multidomain Data-Plane (MDP) jointly with an AI-driven multi-stakeholder interdomain Control-Plane. This will enable the creation of E2E deterministic paths.

To enhance the predictability of the network through intelligence enabling the forecasting of the occupancy of network resources and the effect of accepting a new flow into the network.

Our Objectives

Design a deterministic network

Define a deterministic (reliable, time sensitive, and predictable) multi-technology and multi-stakeholder network to provide the PREDICT-6G network architecture based on the analysis of relevant use cases, evaluating its potential business impact.

Reliability, time sensitiveness & predictability

Design a Multi-technology, multi-domain Data-Plane to improve the level of reliability and time sensitiveness that is achievable at different technology domains, while enabling predictability of their behavior.

AI-based control-plane framework

Provide a novel AI-based control-plane framework to enable determinism in multi-stakeholder multi-technology 6G environments. As well as to control, manage and orchestrate network devices and resources beyond traditional Software Defined Network approaches.

Test the system architecture

Integration, experimentation and use case verification to integrate the data- and control-plane components developed in PREDICT-6G in order to build working prototypes implementing the services, functionalities and workflows specified in the system architecture.

Reach the largest number of people

Disseminate and communicate project results to the broadest audience using Open Science practices, impact standards and European ecosystem, and exploit project outcomes.